

Learning Spaces as Living Labs in Dutch River Management: Joint effort to improve river management through innovation

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Abstract

To facilitate innovation in Dutch river management, the river authority has launched the concept of 'Learning Spaces'. These learning spaces function as living labs in bringing different stakeholders from the quadruple helix together. The team collects and tests innovative ideas and prepares them both technically and socially for implementation. Tools to monitor the progress are Stakeholder Readiness Levels and Portfolio Management. During the first learning space period 8 innovations have been tested, some have moved towards implementation, and some to a next research phase. However, the innovation with most impact is possibly the learning space itself. It is included in any performance contracts of the river authority, and as such has become a standardized form of cooperation.

Keywords

Innovation Team, Rhine, Operational Management, Quadruple Helix

Problem statement

Rijkswaterstaat initiated in 2014 so-called Learning Spaces in the Dutch branches of the River Rhine (1,2). Learning Spaces are innovative forms of Living Labs as they are part of multi-year maintenance contracts between Rijkswaterstaat and a contractor, and in which knowledge institutes are invited to participate. Furthermore, the connection to the maintenance contract gives the living lab direct access to real-life challenges to be addressed and an experimental space. The aim of the living lab is to develop innovations improving efficiency and sustainability of river management (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The focus and design of a Learning Space (source: Rijkswaterstaat)

Since 2020, Learning Spaces are a contractually approved instrument, and included in any new river maintenance contract. In this paper we aim to analyse how the Learning Spaces contribute to innovation and knowledge development. In particular we are interested in supporting the partners in this new way of working as well as improving the knowledge development and learning process.

Methods used

This paper is the result of action research. Two of the authors participate in a Learning Space, both in the operational teams (the ‘Innovation Teams’) and as coordinators. For this paper, we draw on our experiences in or with the Learning Spaces and on documents developed by the Innovation Teams, complemented with interviews with other participants. Innovations are collected and their progressed tracked with Technological Readiness Level assessments, Stakeholder Readiness Level assessments (3), and portfolio management.

Results/outcomes

The study shows that Learning Spaces provide a new, both promising and challenging way of working. In the first Learning Space, up to 8 innovations have been tested or supported in multiple ways, leaving space for initiatives from different partners. The Learning Spaces have increased both the technological and stakeholder readiness levels, but the extent to which differs per innovation. Furthermore, the most successful innovation is maybe the instrument itself: Learning Spaces are now an approved and established instrument in Rijkswaterstaat. At this point in time at least 8 new Learning Spaces have been launched and more will follow when new maintenance contracts start, both in river and road management.

Interest to the audience

This paper discusses an innovative form of Living Labs and it demonstrates how a Living Lab could be institutionalized. Furthermore, instruments like Stakeholder Readiness levels and Portfolio Management may interest the audience.

What we would like to get out of the presentation

The learning spaces have become the new standard in Dutch river management. We would like to substantiate the way we work. Which theories are useful to further analyse the living labs, how could we improve the quality of the living labs and improve learning within the involved organisations?

References

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